

INTELLEKTUAL TRANSPORT TIZIMLARINING ILOVALARI ISH FAOLIYATINI YAXSHILASH UCHUN TRAFFIKNI BASHORAT QILISH

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Annotatsiya. Maqola aqlli transport tizimlarida amalga oshirilishi mumkin bo'lgan transport bashorati bilan bog'liq bo'lib, u o'tgan yilgi ma'lumotlar to'plami va so'nggi yil ma'lumotlari o'rtasidagi prognozni o'z ichiga oladi, natijada aniqlik va o'rtacha kvadrat xatoni ta'minlaydi. Ushbu bashorat zudlik bilan tirbandlik holatini tekshirishga muhtoj bo'lgan odamlar uchun foydali bo'ladi. Trafik ma'lumotlari 1 soatlik vaqt oralig'i asosida taxmin qilinadi. Ushbu bashoratdan trafikning jonli statistikasi tahlil qilinadi. Shunday qilib, avtomobil foydalanuvchilari yo'lda ketayotganda buni tahlil qilish osonroq bo'ladi. Tizim barcha yo'llarning ma'lumotlarini taqqoslaydi va shaharning eng ko'p aholi gavjum yo'llarini aniqlaydi. Maqolada Sklearn, Keras va Tensorflow kutubxonalarini import qilish orqali mashinali o'qitishdan foydalangan holda trafikni bashorat qilish uchun regressiya modelini taklif qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: trafik, regressiya, intellektual transport tizimi (ITT), mashinali o'qitish, bashorat qilish

Kirish. Mashinali o'qitish (ML) bugungi kunda eng muhim va ommabop rivojlanayotgan tarmoqlardan biri bo'lib, u sun'iy intellektning (SI) bir qismidir. So'nggi paytlarda mashinali o'qitish transport muhandisligi, ayniqsa transportni bashorat qilishda muhim va kelgusi tadqiqot sohasiga aylandi. Yo'l harakati tirbandligi o'z vositalari bilan bevosita yoki bilvosita mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga ta'sir

qiladi. Yo‘l tirbandligi ham odamlarning qimmatli vaqtini yo‘qotishiga va vaqtini sarlashiga sabab bo‘ladi. Mamlakatning iqtisodiy o‘shini ta‘minlash uchun birinchi navbatda yo‘l harakati foydalanuvchilari uchun qulaylik talab etiladi.

Mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga qo‘shimcha ravishda, ifloslanishni ham kamaytirish mumkin. Hukumat ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun intellektual transport tizimiga (ITT) sarmoya kiritmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqot ishining maqsadi turli xil mashinalarni o‘qitish algoritmlarini topish va python3 dan foydalangan holda modellarni taxmin qilishdir. Hozirgi vaqtda transport juda qizg‘in bo‘lib bormoqda va buni odamlar yo‘lda bo‘lganida aniqlab bo‘lmaydi. Shunday qilib, ushbu tadqiqot trafikni bashorat qilish uchun foydali bo‘lishi mumkin. Mashinali o‘qitish odatda anaconda dasturi yordamida amalga oshiriladi, ammo bu maqolada men python dasturidan buyruq satri oynasidan foydalanganman, bu ma‘lumotlarni taxmin qilishning odatdagi usulidan ancha osondir.

Yo‘l harakati bashorati tahlili. Trafik oqimini bashorat qilishning maqsadi foydalanuvchilarga imkon qadar tezroq tirbandlikni bashorat qilishdir. Hozirgi vaqtda transport tirbandligi juda muammo bo‘lib bormoqda va buni odamlar yo‘lda bo‘lganida aniqlab bo‘lmaydi.

Trafik tirbandligini bashorat qilishda ma‘lumotlarni yig‘ish va bashorat qilish modeli.

1– rasm. Yo‘l harakati prognozi modeli

Bashorat qilishda hech qanday kamchiliklar bo'lmashi uchun metodologiya to'g'ri bajarilishi kerak. Ma'lumotlar yig'ilgandan so'ng, ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash muhim rol o'ynaydi, bu esa kirish sifatida qabul qilingan ma'lumotlar to'plamini o'qitish va sinab ko'rishdir. Ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlagandan so'ng, kerakli modellar yordamida tasdiqlash amalga oshiriladi. 1-rasmda Mashinali o'qitishdan foydalangan holda trafikni bashorat qilish modeli ko'rsatilgan.

Metodologiya. Ko'pgina tadqiqotchilar muhokama qilingan turli xil yondashuvlardan foydalanganlar. Ushbu maqolada Pandas, Numpy, OS, Matplotlib.pyplot, Keras va Sklearn kabi turli kutubxonalar yordamida regressiya modeli yordamida trafikni bashorat qilish texnikasi mavjud.

Ma'lumotlar to'plami. Ayni kunlarda transport tirbandligi ko'paymoqda. Shahar aholisining kengayishi, muvofiqlashtirilmagan svetofor va real vaqtda ma'lumotlarning yetishmasligi tirbandlikni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Ikkita ma'lumotlar to'plami to'plangan, ulardan biri 2019 yilgi yo'l harakati ma'lumotlari bo'lib, ular sana, vaqt va transport vositalari, chorrahalar soni, qolganlari esa hech qanday noto'g'ri tushunchalarsiz osongina solishtirish uchun bir xil tafsilotlarga ega 2021 yilgi yo'l harakati ma'lumotlaridir. Har bir 1 soatlik interval bilan transport oqimini bashorat qilishni hisoblash uchun 1 dan 24 soatgacha vaqt oralig'ida jamlangan ma'lumotlarni oldindan qayta ishlash orqali keraksiz ma'lumotlar o'chirildi.

Regressiya modeli. Regressiya model tahlili hatto bitta bog'liq o'zgaruvchisi va bir yoki bir nechta mustaqil o'zgaruvchilar o'rtasida bog'lanishni hal qilishning matematik usuli bo'lishi mumkin.

2– rasm. Trafikni bashorat qilishning regressiya modeli

Baholash bashorat qiluvchilarning skalyar vektorlari yig'indisidan kelib chiqqan holda model uchun bashorat qilingan qiymatni beradi. Anqlik o'rtacha kvadrat xatoni hisoblash orqali o'lchanadi. Shunday qilib, kuzatilgan qiymatdan kutilgan xatoni, shuningdek, statistik usullarda qo'llaniladigan standart og'ishga teng bo'lgan haqiqat qiymatini olish. 2-rasmda Trafikni bashorat qilish uchun regressiya modeli ko'rsatilgan.

Biz to'rtta ulanishning ma'lumotlar to'plamini o'rganamiz va xuddi shu yo'nalishdagi trafikni bashorat qilish uchun modelni yaratamiz. Bu muammoni bartaraf etish uchun infratuzilmani qurishda yordam beradigan transport shakllarini yaxshiroq tushunish orqali tirbandlik muammosini hal qilishda yordam berishi mumkin.

```

✓ [5] # Importing Libraries
0 cek. import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import datetime
import tensorflow
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from tensorflow import keras
from keras import callbacks
from tensorflow.keras import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D, Flatten, Dense, LSTM, Dropout, GRU, Bidirectional
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers.legacy import SGD
import math
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error

import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")

✓ [21] data = pd.read_csv("../content/traffic.csv")
0 cek. data.head()

```

3-rasm. Kutubxonalarni import qilish va ma'lumotlarni yuklash

Indeks	Sana_Vaqti	Chorraha	Avtomobillar	ID
0	2019-11-01 00:00:00	1	15	20191101001
1	2019-11-01 01:00:00	1	13	20191101011
2	2019-11-01 02:00:00	1	10	20191101021
3	2019-11-01 03:00:00	1	7	20191101031
4	2019-11-01 04:00:00	1	9	20191101041

1-jadval. Yig'ilgan ma'lumotlarning dastlabki ko'rinishi

Ushbu ma'lumotlar to'plami to'rtta chorrahadagi avtomobillarning soatlik hisobi to'plamidir. CSV faylida to'rtta xususiyat mavjud:

- Sana_Vaqti
- Chorraha
- Avtomobillar
- ID

Har bir chorrahadagi sensorlar turli vaqtlarda ma'lumotlarni yig'ishganligi sababli, trafik ma'lumotlari bir necha vaqt oralig'ida keladi.

4-rasm. Yillar davomida chorrhalardagi harakatning visual ko‘rinishi
Bashorat qilishdan olingan natijalar:

```
#!/bin/sh chorraha bashorat qilish
Pred1 = GRU_model(x_train1,y_train1,x_test1)

Epoch 1/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.076400000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 454.300ms/Step - loss: 0.0764
Epoch 2/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.063600000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 355.400ms/Step - loss: 0.0636
Epoch 3/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.062400000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 355.400ms/Step - loss: 0.0624
Epoch 4/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.061200000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0612
Epoch 5/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.060000000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0600
Epoch 6/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.058800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0588
Epoch 7/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.057600000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0576
Epoch 8/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.056400000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0564
Epoch 9/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.055200000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0552
Epoch 10/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.054000000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0540
Epoch 11/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.052800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.0528
```


5-rasm. Birinchi chorraha uchun GRU tirbandlik prognozi va haqiqiy qiymat

```
#!/bin/sh chorraha uchun bashoralar
Pred2 = GRU_model(x_train2,y_train2,x_test2)

Epoch 1/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.229800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 459.400ms/Step - loss: 0.2298
Epoch 2/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.208400000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 344.300ms/Step - loss: 0.2084
Epoch 3/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.197000000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 364.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1970
Epoch 4/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.196600000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1966
Epoch 5/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.193700000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 355.300ms/Step - loss: 0.1937
Epoch 6/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.193700000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 355.300ms/Step - loss: 0.1937
Epoch 7/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.193700000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1937
Epoch 8/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.189800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1898
Epoch 9/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.188800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 355.300ms/Step - loss: 0.1888
Epoch 10/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.189800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1898
Epoch 11/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.189800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.1898
```


6-rasm. Ikkinchi chorraha uchun GRU tirbandlik prognozi va haqiqiy qiymat

```
#!/bin/sh chorraha uchun bashoralar
Pred3 = GRU_model(x_train3,y_train3,x_test3)

Epoch 1/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.300800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 485.420ms/Step - loss: 0.3008
Epoch 2/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.293800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 385.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2938
Epoch 3/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.290800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2908
Epoch 4/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.291800000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 385.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2918
Epoch 5/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.289300000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 365.400ms/Step - loss: 0.2893
Epoch 6/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.286900000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2869
Epoch 7/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.288700000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2887
Epoch 8/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.289200000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2892
Epoch 9/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.289200000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2892
Epoch 10/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.285100000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 375.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2851
Epoch 11/50
88/88 [====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.284700000000000000:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric 'val_loss' which is not available.
88/88 [====] - 385.420ms/Step - loss: 0.2847
```


7-rasm. Uchinchi chorraha uchun GRU tirbandlik prognozi va haqiqiy qiymat

```

Predik + GRU_model(x_train(x,y_train(x,y_test(x))
Epoch 1/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6983WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 109 41864/step - loss: 0.6903
Epoch 2/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6950WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 109 37286/step - loss: 0.6950
Epoch 3/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6870WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 109 39206/step - loss: 0.6870
Epoch 4/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6821WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 111 41546/step - loss: 0.6821
Epoch 5/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6803WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 111 41886/step - loss: 0.6803
Epoch 6/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6853WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 111 42286/step - loss: 0.6857
Epoch 7/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6880WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 109 39866/step - loss: 0.6889
Epoch 8/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6853WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 109 39086/step - loss: 0.6815
Epoch 9/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6820WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 111 42186/step - loss: 0.6820
Epoch 10/50 ..... - ETA: 0s - loss: 0.6793WARNING:tensorflow:Early stopping conditioned on metric `val_loss` which is not available.
26/26 ..... - 111 42086/step - loss: 0.6793
Epoch 11/50
    
```


8-rasm. To‘rtinchi chorraha uchun GRU tirbandlik prognozi va haqiqiy qiymat

2-jadval: Ma’lumotlarni o‘qitishdan olingan natija

Chorrahalar	O‘rtacha kvadratik xatosi
1	0.24611639258595508
2	0.6061582552003247
3	0.6061582552003247
4	1.0034960152772239

Xulosa sifatida, ushbu maqolada mashinali o‘qitishdan foydalangan holda yo‘l harakati prognozi shaharlardagi tirbandliklarni hal qilish uchun samarali yechimdir. Katta hajmdagi trafik ma’lumotlari mavjudligi bilan Mashinali o‘qitish algoritmlari real vaqtda transport oqimi va tirbandliklarni aniq bashorat qilishi mumkin. Ushbu bashoratlardan transport oqimini optimallashtirish va transport tizimlarining umumiy samaradorligini oshirish uchun foydalanish mumkin. Mashinali o‘qitishdan foydalangan holda yo‘l harakati prognozi bilan bog‘liq ba’zi qiyinchiliklar mavjud bo‘lsada foyda sezilarli bo‘lib, transport tizimlarini yaxshilashga va iqtisodiy yo‘qotishlarni kamaytirishga olib kelishi mumkin.

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